

Studies in Acetyl Bromide as a Polar Solvent. Part I. Solubility of Substances, Formation of Solvates, and Electrical Conductance of Solutions

Ram Chand Paul, Sarjit Singh Sandhu, and Jagtar Singh Bassi

Solubilities of several substances including a few Lewis acids, bromides, and organic tertiary bases have been tried in acetyl bromide and the formation of solvates in this solvent has been studied. Solutions of the Lewis acids and bases in acetyl bromide have been found conducting, which indicates the formation of ion pairs. The constitution of these solutions has been discussed.

The physical properties of acetyl bromide, *i.e.*, dielectric constant 16.5 at 20° (International Critical Tables, 1929, VI, p. 84), *m.p.* -96.5°, *b.p.* 76.7° (Handbook of Chemistry & Physics, Chemical Rubber Publishing Company, 39th ed., 1957-58, p. 725), electrical conductance 2×10^{-8} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (International Critical Tables, 1929, VI, p. 143), and relatively long carbonyl-bromine bond 2.00 Å as compared to methyl bromide, 1.936 Å (Allen and Suttén, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, 47, 236), are suggestive of a slightly polar character of the solvent. The work, which is being reported in this and the subsequent parts, supports the auto-ionisation of acetyl bromide as :

Solubility of the substances in this liquid reveals that, in general, only the covalent compounds are soluble while ionic compounds are insoluble; this is expected of the solvents having a low dielectric constant. Solubility of the compounds has been studied quantitatively and in some cases qualitatively. The results are presented in Tables IA and IB. The Lewis acids and bases mostly dissolve to form coloured solutions in acetyl bromide, indicating formation of complexes in solution. Pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, isoquinoline, and triethylamine are sparingly soluble and form solid solvates, which are discussed later on.

Literature records the formation of a monosolvate by *NN*-dimethylformamide with acetyl bromide (Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2717). Acetyl bromide forms solid solvates with organic tertiary bases and cadmium bromide. Pyridine, when mixed with ice-cold acetyl bromide, yields a very deliquescent red solid. Methylpyridines, except α -picoline and isoquinoline, also yields monosolvates, which are hygroscopic in nature. Cadmium bromide forms an unstable disolvate, which loses acetyl bromide slowly, and an intermediate solvate, 2CdBr₂·3AcBr, has been analysed, which later on loses more of acetyl bromide under vacuum to yield a slightly more stable solvate, 2CdBr₂·AcBr. The solvates isolated and the analytical results obtained are recorded in Table II.

TABLE IA

Quantitative solubilities in acetyl bromide at 30° ± 1°.

Compound.	Solubility (g./100 g. solvent).	Colour of solution.	Heat effect.	Compound.	Solubility (g./100 g. solvent).	Colour of solution.	Heat effect.
SbBr ₃	120.3 g.	Black	..	AsBr ₃	Miscible	Orange	..
SnBr ₄	Miscible	..	..	α -Picoline	..	Red	Exothermic
TiBr ₄	..	Red	Exothermic	Quinoline	..	..	..
PBr ₃	..	..	..	Dimethylaniline	..	Light yellow	..
H ₂ Br ₂	0.772 g.	Dark red	..	AlBr ₃	..	Dark-red	..

TABLE IB

Qualitative solubilities.

Compound.	Solubility.	Colour.	Heat effect.
Bi_2O_3	Appreciable	Red	Exothermic
SeO_2	Highly soluble	Dark red	"
CdO	Insoluble	Light yellow	"
CdCO_3	"	"	"
Li_2CO_3	"	"	"
AgNO_3	"	Reddish yellow	Exothermic
KNO_3	"	Yellow	Slightly exothermic
Na_2CO_3	"	Red	Exothermic.
$\text{Na}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})$	"	Light yellow	"
$\text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	Soluble	Black	"
Pyridine.	Sparingly soluble	Red	"
β -Picoline	" "	"	"
γ -Picoline	" "	Yellow	"
Isoquinoline	" "	"	"

Note: Miscible means freely soluble. Sparingly soluble and appreciably soluble signify the solubility of about 5% and 15% respectively.

TABLE II

Solvate formation.

Compound.	Solvate.	Colour.	Found.	Ratio.	Calc.	Ratio.
Pyridine	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$	Red	*Base: 22.25 Br: 23.75	0.983	Base: 39.10 Br: 39.60	0.987
β -Picoline	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$	"	Base: 33.12 Br: 26.37	1.25	Base: 23.05 Br: 37.03	1.16
γ -Picoline	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$	Yellow	Base: 29.16 Br: 23.43	1.22	Base: 43.05 Br: 37.03	1.16
Isoquinoline	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$	"	Base: 40.03 Br: 25.95	1.54	Base: 51.19 Br: 31.76	1.61
NN-Dimethyl-formamide	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{CON} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$	..	..	..	(loc. cit.) ¹⁰	..
Cadmium bromide	(i) $2\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$	Dirty white	Cd: 24.23 Br: 59.67	..	Cd: 24.30 Br: 61.40	..
	(ii) $2\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$	"	Cd: 33.70 Br: 58.36	..	Cd: 33.63 Br: 59.89	..

* The difference in the analytical results actually found and those calculated is due to the inert solvent, which has been used as a wash liquid and has been allowed to remain with the compound. The ratio of base/bromine in these cases is close enough to confirm the composition of the compounds.

The constitution of these solvates and of the solutions containing the Lewis acids and bases in acetyl bromide may be profitably discussed by taking into consideration the electrical properties of the solutions. The specific conductance of the Lewis acids, bases, and quaternary ammonium bromides has been determined in acetyl bromide at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III

*Specific conductance of the solutions of the Lewis acids and bases in acetyl bromide.*Specific conductance of acetyl bromide = 2×10^{-6} mhos.

Substance.	Conc. (mol./litre).	Conduc. (mhos).	Substance.	Conc. (mol./litre).	Conduc. (mhos).
Pyridine	0.01665	6.630×10^{-5}	Isoquinoline	0.00770	4.2900×10^{-5}
α -Picoline	0.01379	1.682×10^{-4}	SnBr ₄	0.00228	8.0325×10^{-5}
β -Picoline	0.01108	0.531×10^{-4}	SbBr ₃	0.01973	1.9460×10^{-5}
γ -Picoline	0.00428	2.3625×10^{-5}	Et ₄ NBr	0.01440	6.4200×10^{-4}

The specific conductance of the solutions of quaternary ammonium bromides in acetyl bromide indicates their strong ionisation in acetyl bromide; the result is almost comparable to that of potassium bromide in aqueous solutions. This increase in conductance of acetyl bromide in presence of these bromides is very likely due to the feeble ionisation of acetyl bromide to produce Br⁻ and Ac⁺ ions. The addition of bromides results in an increase in the concentration of bromide ions, which conduct current. The mode of ionisation is exemplified as:

Stannic bromide, which has been used as a Lewis acid in arsenic tribromide (Jander and Guenther, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1958, **297**, 81; 1959, **298**, 241), does not form any solid solvate with acetyl bromide and same is true of antimony tribromide. Of course, their addition to acetyl bromide enhances the specific conductance of the latter. The increase in conductance is presumably due to the formation of solvates in solution and their subsequent ionisation to provide acetylum ions as:

The increase in conductance of acetyl bromide in presence of α -picoline, quinoline, and dimethylaniline, which do not form solid solvates under ordinary experimental conditions, is indeed interesting. These substances having tertiary nitrogen are presumed to form, in solution, solvates, which ionise furnishing cations containing quadrivalent nitrogen. Thus increase in conductance is due to the formation of strongly polar compounds, which furnish ions to conduct current. Bromide ions, which are considerably mobile, are more effective in carrying current.

Similarly, the formation of solvates in solution and their subsequent ionisation are responsible for the increase in conductance of acetyl bromide when quinoline and dimethylaniline are added to the solution.

The solvates of pyridine, isoquinoline, β -picoline, and γ -picoline, which are only slightly soluble in acetyl bromide, also enhance the conductance of acetyl bromide thus:

Behaviour of organic tertiary bases in acetyl chloride and benzoyl chloride has already been explained on similar lines (Paul *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 315; this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 195).

EXPERIMENTAL

Crude acetyl bromide was fractionated in an all-glass apparatus using a long fractionating column. The fraction distilling at 73-75°/735 mm was collected, treated with purified dimethylaniline (1% by weight), and again fractionated using a long vacuum jacketed fractionating column filled with glass beads. The fraction coming at 74°/735 mm was collected. The distillate was further treated with freshly cut small pieces of sodium metal and distilled at a take-off ratio 1:10. Tertiary organic bases were purified as described previously (Paul *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1959).

To determine solubility of the various compounds in acetyl bromide, the latter was added with the help of a jet to a well-dried ampoule containing sufficient quantity of the compound; but if the reaction was exothermic, the solid was added in small amounts to the thoroughly cooled acetyl bromide contained in the ampoule. The ampoule was immediately sealed and shaken in a thermostat controlled by a toluene regulator at 30° ± 0.1° for 24 hours. The ampoule was broken and the slurry formed was filtered quickly through a sintered glass funnel in absence of moisture. Solubility of the substance in 100 g. of acetyl bromide was determined by estimating the cation from the known weight of the solution.

The solvates of acetyl bromide with organic bases are mostly unstable. In such cases the thoroughly cooled base was slowly added to ice-cooled acetyl bromide contained in a standard joint test tube with the help of a dropper. After keeping the mixture in an ice bath for 2 hours, the solid was separated by filtration in a dry atmosphere and washed with dry benzene or dry petroleum ether. The compounds could not be kept under vacuum as these decomposed. The compounds were analysed as such. Bromine was estimated as silver bromide while bases were estimated by the Jackson-Smith method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 544).

Cadmium bromide (5 g.) was treated with acetyl bromide (20 c.c.) in a sealed ampoule. The reaction mixture was shaken in a thermostat at 30° ± 0.1° for about 24 hours. The solid was separated by filtration and washed with dry benzene. Traces of the solvent were removed by keeping the solid under vacuum for 5 minutes. The solid was analysed when cadmium was estimated as cadmium molybdate and bromine as silver bromide. (Found: Cd, 24.23; Br, 59.67. $2\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$ requires Cd, 24.3; Br, 61.4%).

The solvate was kept under vacuum for 2 hours and then again analysed. The results of analysis lead to the formula, $2\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$. (Found: Cd, 33.7; Br, 58.36. $2\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$ requires Cd, 33.63; Br, 59.89%).

Conductivity Outfit.—Precision measuring bridge type WBR. No. 108 with logarithmic amplifier type TAV, IKC, No. 034, manufactured by Wissenschaftlich Technische Werkstätten Wielheim/Oby., Germany, was used for determining conductance of the solutions. A solution of concentration about 0.01 moles/litre of different substances in acetyl bromide was directly prepared in the conductivity cell of a cell constant 0.315. All measurements were made at 30° ± 0.1° by placing the conductivity cell in a thermostat regulated to that temperature.